

Research Methods and Tools – Report 3

Deliverable 2.5

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RE-DWELL

Deliverable 2.5 Research Methods and Tools – Report 3

Version 1

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Executive summary

This report provides an overview of the content, structure, and outcomes of the Research Methods and Tools course "Transferring research findings to community" (RMT3), conducted from March to October 2023. It ran in parallel with the "Transferable Skills" (TS3) course, which was aligned with on-going work on WP4 "Transdisciplinary affordable and sustainable housing research framework". This alignment enhanced collaborative efforts across individual research projects and facilitated transdisciplinary research within the network. The Centre for Social Sciences (CSS) led the planning and delivery of this course, collaborating with other project partners in the design and implementation of learning activities.

The course is worth 4 ECTS, which is equivalent to about 100 hours of learning, including online and in-person sessions and self-directed work.

RMT3, the final module in the RE-DWELL research and methods course series, aims to establish a transdisciplinary theoretical foundation for ESRs. It focuses on equipping ESRs with skills to effectively communicate research findings to non-academic partners involved in developing sustainable housing solutions. The module covers various methods, explores their applicability in transdisciplinary research, guides researchers in methodological linking of secondment work, promotes collaboration, and enhances ESRs' ability to interlink diverse research threads within the network.

RMT3 featured two tasks aligned with key research areas:

- **Task 1. Classification of stakeholders and methods.** ESRs collaboratively identified non-academic groups and methods to transfer knowledge based on their secondments. This involved mapping target groups, presenting effective communication methods, and exploring overlaps among target groups.

- **Task 2. Identification of gaps and challenges.** The focus was on understanding national differences and gaps in methodologies for information, collection and dissemination of research outputs, considering local contexts. Activities included describing experiences in presenting research findings, discussing challenges in data analysis, and addressing disciplinary and national disparities in research transfer.

The tasks informed TS3 and contributed to WP4. Lectures and discussions were held online and in-person during the Zagreb Workshop and the Reading Summer School.

Participants assessed the course through an online survey, and detailed results can be found in Annex 1.

1. Introduction

The purpose of this report is to document the work carried out in the course Research Methods and Tools “Transferring research findings to community” (RMT3). The report encompasses the aims, learning outcomes, structures, content, learning activities, resources and outputs of the course. RMT3 is the last of a three-module course focused on research methodologies and tools.

Given the close relationship between RMT3 and TS3 “Communication and dissemination; Engagement and impact”, both courses ran concurrently (see Deliverable 2.8). The tasks for each course were interconnected and complementary. Moreover, they were aligned with the tasks outlined in WP4 “Transdisciplinary Research Framework” (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Connections between RMT3/TS3 and WP4

RMT3 received input from and delivered input to various RE-DWELL network activities and deliverables, notably the Zagreb Workshop (WS3) and the Reading Summer School (SS3). The course drew on project outputs such as case studies, vocabulary, secondment reports, blog posts, publications, and ESR project summaries.

The course was prepared and delivered by Centre for Social Sciences (CSS). The planning of the sessions during WS3 and SS3 was discussed with the organisers of these events, Institute for Social Policy and the University of Reading, respectively.

This document is structured as follows: Section 2, “Course aims”; Section 3, “Learning outcomes”; Section 4, “Course Structure”; Section 5, “Learning activities”; Section 6, “Resources”; Section 7, “Outputs”; Section 8, “Evaluation”.

The evaluation survey is included in Annex 1.

2. Course aims

RMT3 “Transferring research findings to community”, is the third and final module in a series of three research and methods courses which aim to foster an appropriate theoretical foundation of the ESR’s research projects in a transdisciplinary manner. The objective of this module is to equip ESRs with the necessary skills to convey their research findings effectively to the non-academic organizations they are partnered with. The course concentrated on engaging key stakeholders in the design, planning, and provision of sustainable and affordable housing solutions.

Specifically, this module has the following learning aims:

- To introduce various methods to transfer research findings
- To explore the applicability of methods in transdisciplinary research
- To provide researchers with guidance on the methodological linking of secondment work
- To foster cooperation among researchers to strengthen collaborative research
- To improve the ability of ESRs to interlink the diverse threads of work within the collaborative research network

3. Learning outcomes

Upon successfully completing the RMT3 module, ESRs will demonstrate the following outcomes:

- Ability to effectively interact with external stakeholders, including non-academic sectors, local administrations, and civic organizations, particularly in the context of sustainable and affordable housing initiatives
- An understanding of diverse communication methods, enabling them to tailor their approaches to specific non-academic groups
- Ability to select the most suitable communication methods to convey housing research findings across different disciplines to specific target groups
- Ability to position their own research results and those of other ESRs within the context of targeted stakeholders, ensuring that their findings are appropriately communicated and understood by the intended audience
- Ability to prepare transdisciplinary dissemination proposals that consider the needs and perspectives of all relevant stakeholders
- A comprehensive understanding of the transdisciplinary approach to sustainable and affordable housing, including the importance of interdisciplinary collaboration, effective communication and active engagement of all stakeholders involved
- A thorough understanding of the transdisciplinary approach, encompassing interdisciplinary collaboration, communication strategies, and stakeholder engagement

4. Course structure

RMT3 is structured in two main tasks which were carried out throughout the course in different teaching and learning contexts. Due to the close relationship between RMT3 and TS3, some of the tasks in both courses were complementary.

Task 1. Classification of stakeholders and methods

The ESRs identified non-academic groups and methods for knowledge transfer derived from or associated with their secondments.

Task 1 included the following activities:

- To identify the target groups (actors, non-academic organisations) which might be interested in the results of the work conducted during the secondment
- To document the methods used to disseminate scientific results to non-academic organisations, both during and after the secondment
- To give a short presentation (5 minutes) on the most effective method and tool to communicate their research findings
- To produce a map focusing on a section of the target group landscape derived from their experiences during the secondment
- To identify overlaps and similarities among their respective target groups, enhancing their understanding of potential collaborations and shared interests
- To engage in reflections concerning the interactions between the three research areas, aiming to foster a transdisciplinary approach in their research endeavours

The communication tools identified in this task were used by the TS3 module, and the reflections on the interactions between the three research areas were incorporated into Tasks 4.1, 4.2 and 4.3 in Work Package 4.

Task 2. Identification of gaps and challenges

The objective of this task was to support the successful completion of individual research projects and to contribute to TS3 and WP4.

The ESRs explored national differences and gaps in methodology useful for collecting information, as well as selecting the appropriate methods for disseminating empirical research results. They also considered local, national and urban specificities that might influence the effectiveness of methods used to study various research topics.

Task 2 encompassed the following activities:

- A description of how the team presented research findings to stakeholders, highlighting the methods used and challenges faced. It includes the strategies employed to communicate the research process and results, as well as the techniques used to identify target groups and the feedback received
- An explanation of the challenges encountered in analysing and preparing the data for presentation to secondment organisations, with a focus on evaluating the effectiveness of the methods used

- A discussion of the elements of research transfer, considering disciplinary disparities and national differences in the application of dissemination methods

To foster collaborative reflection while carrying out these two tasks, the ESRs organized themselves into teams of three, focusing on the three RE-DWELL key research areas: 1. Design, planning and building; 2. Community participation; and 3. Policy and financing. The composition of teams was determined by mutual agreement among the ESRs.

In both tasks, the ESRs utilized a variety of communication tools and incorporated project outputs, such as secondment reports, blog posts, case studies, and specialized vocabulary terms, to enhance their knowledge dissemination efforts.

Around the two tasks, there have been lectures and discussions carried out in online and in-person sessions at the Zagreb Workshop and the Reading Summer School. Figure 2 shows the timeline for the RMT3 course, including the connections to TS3 and to other RE-DWELL activities.

Figure 2. RMT3 courses structure as integrated with the network activities

The course employed a blend of asynchronous and synchronous learning methods, encompassing both online and in-person components. The course was inaugurated during WS3 with a session covering the course's introduction, structure, goals, activities, and tasks. This included a hands-on workshop delving into various methods for engaging non-academic groups. Subsequent online sessions focused on research methods. Additionally, a lecture during SS3 provided insights into Post-Occupancy Evaluation (POE), complemented by a hands-on workshop aimed at investigating gaps and challenges in the research results transfer process.

Table 1 provides an overview of the programme structure, timetable and facilitators. Further formation is provided in Section 5 “Learning activities”.

Table1. RMT3 sessions briefs

Sessions	Activities	Facilitators
	Independent work: Preparation for RMT3 kick-off Workshop session at Zagreb. Assignment in preparation of Session 2 : Identifying non-academic groups and methods for knowledge transfer.	ESRs
30.3.2023 Workshop 3	Session 1: Introduction to the RMT3 course (goals, structure, planning, activities and collaborative work for ESRs and expected deliverables). Session 2: Classification of stakeholders and methods. Mapping a section of target group landscape based on the experience during secondment. Group work: Identifying overlaps and similarities between ESRs target groups. Reflections on the interactions between the 3 research areas to foster the transdisciplinary research.	Adrienne Csizmady Adrienne Csizmady Lorraine Farrelly ESRs
March-May 2023 Online	Group and independent work towards further development of the map.	ESRs
April-June 2023 Online	Session 3: Exploring innovative methodologies and tools Session 4: Stakeholder interviews and results Session 5: Researching the housing position of vulnerable social groups Session 6: Focus groups Session 7: Smart Social Sciences	Endre Sik Gergely Olt József Hegedüs Joris Hoekstra Bence Ságvári and Bence Kollány

May-July 2023 Online	Preparation for Summer School: Short presentation for on the challenges in transferring research results to non-academic groups	ESRs
3-4.7.2023 Summer School 3	<p>Session 8: Lecture on methods of post occupancy evaluation</p> <p>Session 9: ESRs presentation on the challenges in transferring research results to non-academic groups</p> <p>Group work: Discuss elements of transferring research results, disciplinarily differences, and national differences in using dissemination methods</p>	Gloria Vargas Adrienne Csizmady and Lorraine Farrelly ESRs
July-Aug. 2023	<p>Group and independent work towards completion of Task 2</p> <p>Finalization of the dissemination plan developed during RMT3 and TS3 to be included in the TS3 deliverable</p>	ESRs
Sept. 2023	Joint presentation with TS3	Lorraine Farrelly and ESRs

The work completed on the course accounted for 4 ECTS (100 hours) in the RE-DWELL training programme which were distributed throughout all the activities (Table2).

Table2. Learning type by type of activity, event and ECTS (1 ECTS= 25 hours)

Events	WS3	Online sessions	SS3
Activities	Hours	Hours	Hours
F2F Lectures Session 8. Methods of Post Occupancy Evaluation	-	-	3
F2F workshops Session 1-2. Introduction to the RMT3 course and Classification of non-academic groups and methods. Session 9. Exploring gaps and challenges in the transfer of research results	3	-	4
Online lectures Session 3. Exploring innovative methodologies and tools	-	2	-
Session 4. Stakeholder interviews and results - barriers and techniques	-	2	-
Session 5. Researching the housing position of vulnerable social groups	-	2	-
Session 6. Focus groups	-	2	-
Session 7. Smart Social Science	-	2	-
Independent learning (80%) Tasks 1 and 2	30	23	27
Total hours	33	33	34

5. Learning activities

RMT3 was carried out from March to October 2023 with sessions that took place in the Zagreb Workshop (March 2023), and in the Reading Summer School (July 2023).

The sessions summarized in Table 1 are described in more detail in the following sub-sections.

5.1. Sessions 1-2: Introduction to the course - Classification of stakeholders and methods (30.3.23)

The sessions took place during the Zagreb workshop.

The RMT3 kick-off session started with an introduction of the course by Adrienne Csizmady. This was followed by a joint hands-on workshop with TS3, facilitated by Adrienne Csizmady and Lorraine Farrelly (Figure 3).

Figure 3. RMT3 kick-off session during the Zagreb workshop

Following the course introduction, the ESRs collaborated in teams of three to reflect on the three research areas. Before the joint session of RMT3 and TS3 in Zagreb, the students were asked to create a presentation in the form of a Miro map, incorporating the actors and non-academic organizations associated with the secondment organizations. This map also detailed the methods employed for disseminating scientific results to non-academic organizations during or after the secondment, along with the effective tools utilized based on their current knowledge.

During the workshop's commencement, the ESRs presented their Task 1 outcomes, which included a map focusing on a segment of the target group landscape derived from their secondment experiences (Figure 4). This presentation laid the groundwork for the ensuing hands-on workshop.

Figure 4. Work in progress Miro map to illustrate the presentation of the groups

Subsequently, in groups of three, the ESRs proceeded to finalize the specifications of target groups, non-academic actors, methods, and communication tools (Figure 5). The primary objective was to establish the connections to the three research areas and uncover overlaps and similarities among the ESRs' target groups. The outcomes of these group discussions were thoroughly examined, and reflections on the interactions between the three research areas were conducted to encourage a transdisciplinary approach in their research endeavours.

Figure 5. Work in groups during RMT3-TS3 joint session

Towards the end of the session, each ESR was tasked with formulating a problem related to their secondment in the form of a concrete question. These questions were then placed on the Miro map, and connections between the three research areas were visually represented and discussed.

Learning aims

- To provide researchers with guidance on the methodological linking of secondment work
- To foster cooperation among researchers to strengthen the collaborative research
- To improve the ability of ESRs to interlink the diverse threads of work within the collaborative research network

Learning outcomes

- An understanding of diverse communication methods, enabling them to tailor their approaches to specific non-academic groups.
- Ability to position their own research results and those of other ESRs within the context of targeted stakeholders, ensuring that their findings are appropriately communicated and understood by the intended audience.

5.2. Session 3 (online) Exploring innovative methodologies and tools (19.3.23)

Endre Sik (CSS) presented some innovative methods to address research questions that cannot be resolved using traditional methods due to their complexity. He showed the advantages of the innovative methodology, using examples from the project. This approach enables the development of a profound understanding of inter-group relations and the influence of the living environment on these relations at the neighbourhood level, grounded strongly in empirical evidence. The methods showcased encompassed walking interviews, mental maps, participatory photography, and the neighbourhood forum.

Figure 6. RMT3 Session 3 (online).

The presentation was followed by a discussion. Students had the opportunity to ask questions about the methods and their concrete application to their own research.

5.3. Session 4: Stakeholder interviews and results - barriers and techniques (25.4.23)

This session took place online on 25 April 2023 (Figure 7). It was delivered by Gergely Olt (CSS) who used his vast experience in conducting qualitative research and publishing the results.

Olt divided his presentation into three main parts: theoretical, technical and practice-oriented. The theoretical segment focused on defining the research objectives and interview questions, as well as the role of stakeholders. The second part centered on techniques and barriers, exploring what can and cannot be researched through fieldwork and interviews. Finally, the third part delved into interpreting results and highlighted the questions one should pose to obtain the

desired outcomes. He emphasized the importance of linking the results to the scientific discourses in which they are discussed. During the session, two successful research examples were presented, alongside two instances of challenges. This served as a learning opportunity, demonstrating how one can glean insights from others' mistakes or their own.

Figure 7. RMT3 Session 4 (online)

Part of this session was focused on organizing interviews with residents with residents to ensure comparability at the neighbourhood level. The ESRs were given the opportunity to ask additional questions related to interviews within the context of their own research topic.

5.4. Session 5: Researching the housing position of vulnerable social groups (16.5.23)

During his presentation, József Hegedüs (CSS) focused on understanding the life strategies of vulnerable groups, using examples of the UPLIFT¹ and HomeLab² projects (Figure 8). . He discussed research and programme evaluation approaches, drawing from studies conducted within two Roma communities and one homeless group.

Hegedüs emphasized fundamental sociological dilemmas, such as choosing between quantitative or qualitative methods, macro or micro perspectives, and actor or structure orientations. He highlighted the effectiveness of blending different research methods and adapting the methodology to suit specific research questions. Using concrete examples from the realm of housing inequality, he underscored the significance of coping strategies, detailing the steps individuals take, as well as the interactions between households and institutional actors.

¹ <https://uplift-youth.eu/>

² <https://homelab.mri.hu/>

During the presentation, he outlined the research strategy of the UPLIFT project, the conceptual framework of the HomeLab pilot project, impact assessment methods, and techniques for measuring the impact of integrated services. He also stressed the importance of the theoretical background group and micro-level hypothesis in research design.

Figure 8. RMT3 Session 5 (online)

The presentation was followed by a discussion. Students had the opportunity to ask questions about the methods and their application to their own research.

5.5. Session 6: Focus groups (23.5.23)

Joris Hoekstra (TUD) examined the advantages and disadvantages of focus group methods in housing (Figure 9). He discussed the differences between interview and focus group methods, as well as the usefulness of focus groups in influencing local policy. Additionally, he provided practical guidance on how to set up a focus group.

Figure 9. RMT3 Session 6 (online)

Following the presentation, a discussion ensued where students had the opportunity to pose questions about the methods and their practical application to their own research.

5.6. Session 7: Smart Social Sciences (12.6.23)

Bence Ságvári (CSS) and Bence Kollányi (CSS), provided a brief introduction to the concept of smart social sciences (Figure 10). They discussed the possibility of enriching surveys with smartphone-based sensor data from the Octopus project³.

During his presentation, Ságvári addressed the challenges of data collection. He highlighted the crisis faced by personal scientific data collection worldwide in recent years, emphasizing that empirical social research is increasingly challenged by the difficulty and cost of implementing this method. Consequently, data collection is shifting towards utilizing "digital footprints" of human behaviour, which can replace or complement certain surveys. He concluded his presentation by discussing the benefits and challenges associated with these methods.

Kollányi introduced the Octopus Research Tools, developed within the National Artificial Intelligence Laboratory (MILAB) at the Social Science Research Centre in Budapest. The Octopus project aims to combine two research methods: sensor and device usage log-based digital behavioural data collection and surveys capable of displaying various multimedia content (audio, images, video) within a sophisticated smartphone-based software ecosystem.

Figure 10. RMT3 Session 7 (online).

Following the presentation, ESRs had the opportunity to discuss the tool's usability for their own research projects. Moreover, they were informed that they will be among the first users of Octopus, providing them with an exclusive chance to engage with the technology.

³ <https://octopus.tk.hu/>

5.7. Session 8: Tools and methods of post-occupancy evaluation (3.7.23)

This session occurred during the Reading Summer School. Gloria Vargas presented POE's tools and methods, emphasizing the process of integrating feedback from residents (Figure 11). The presentation covered survey methods such as questionnaires, interviews, and focus groups. Subsequently, a workshop was conducted as part of the TS3 course.

Figure 11. Gloria Vargas presentation about POE methods and tools

5.8. Session 9: Exploring gaps and challenges in the transfer of research results (4.7.23)

A hands-on workshop was organized during the summer school (Figure 12).

Figure 12. RMT3 session during the Reading Summer School

For this session, the ESRs had prepared a presentation before coming to Reading (Figures 13-14). Working in teams, they discussed various comparative research methodologies, considering their personal preferences and focusing on the three research area.

Figures 13-14. RMT3 Session 9 work in progress presented by ESRs.

The objective of this activity (Task 2) was to identify gaps and challenges in collaborating with external organizations, focusing on the methods employed to gather information related to secondments or PhD theses. The aim was to determine effective methods for sharing specific data and knowledge.

During the session, ESRs discussed methods to engage with local decision-makers and civil society organizations (Figure 15). They explored gaps and challenges, discussing aspects of transferring research findings, considering disciplinary differences, and recognizing national disparities in using dissemination methods. They identified and discussed the most effective ways for communicating their research results to target audiences.

Figure 15. RMT3 hands-on session during the Reading summer school

Learning aims

- To explore the applicability of methods in transdisciplinary research

Learning outcomes

- Ability to prepare transdisciplinary dissemination proposals that consider the needs and perspectives of all relevant stakeholders.
- A comprehensive understanding of the transdisciplinary approach to sustainable and affordable housing, including the importance of interdisciplinary collaboration, effective communication and active engagement of all stakeholders involved.

6. Resources

Learning was facilitated by the resources provided by the lectures and literature recommendations used throughout the different tasks.

The learning materials were available in Teams. The folder structure was the following:

- Course description
- Reading material
- Sessions

Online lectures were recorded and available for later use in Teams.

To support the ESRs a Miro board was developed by the course coordinator.

7. Outputs

The outputs derived from the two tasks were:

- Task 1 (Teamwork): Each team of three created a presentation providing an overview of methods and tools for transferring research findings to non-academic stakeholders, along with a Miro map illustrating their connections
- Task 2 (Teamwork): Each team of three delivered a presentation covering 1) methods of data collection, 2) types of collected data, and 3) challenges in sharing knowledge with professional organizations. They also created a Miro map identifying gaps and challenges in collaborating with external organizations.

8. Course evaluation

ESRs evaluated the RMT3 courses in three contexts: the Zagreb Workshop, the Reading Summer School, and a final evaluation of the course as a whole. The highlights of each evaluation are presented below. Annex 1 contains the result of the final evaluation.

Zagreb Workshop

The online survey for RMT3 session in Zagreb was completed by 9 ESRs and 7 supervisors/co-supervisors, showing the following results (Table 3):

Table 3. RMT3 Summary of the evaluation, Zagreb workshop

Question	Answers	Supervisors /Co-supervisors	ESRs	Average
Day 2 - Thursday 30 - Please evaluate "RMT3 introduction, Adrienne Csizmady" session	16	4.3	3.7	4

The RMT3 session received positive ratings and some positive comments:

"I am so grateful for both Adrienne and Lorraine as they considered all the suggestions we made in the preparation stage of this course. I appreciate that they respected about needs, and it felt that they care about us and our progress."

"This was a good session with information on the upcoming RMT3 course."

"It is good to see that previous feedback and suggestions made by ESRs were taken into account in the design of this module. Also, both TS3 and RMT3 are aligned and have common goals and objectives. This shows that the activities are interlinked and do not develop in silos."

Some positive comments from supervisors/co-supervisors:

"Important to understand the next steps of RMT3."

"Good presentation."

Reading Summer School

The survey of the Reading sessions was completed by 8 ESRs and 9 supervisors/co-supervisors and one partner organisation, showing the following results (Table 4)

Table 4. RMT3 Summary of the evaluation, Reading summer school.

Question	Answers	Supervisors /Co-supervisors	ESRs	Average
Please evaluate the "Tools and methods of POE" session	13	4.5	4.1	4,3
Please evaluate RMT3 session: "Exploring gaps and challenges in the transfer of research results" session	12	4.4	3.9	4,1

The "Tools and Methods of POE" session received positive ratings and comments:

"Very grateful that Dr Gloria Vargas shared all those insights on POE with practical and operational toolboxes. Her work is inspiring for the development of our own methodological approaches."

One supervisor suggested:

"POE and its applications are very relevant for research on housing, however the discussion focused mainly on technical aspects and measurement tools. It would have been interesting to open it up to different applications and adaptations of POE to more qualitative aspects of housing."

One ESR highlighted the value of reflecting on the course but also expressed a limitation due to a shortage of time:

"It was interesting to present our reflections on the RMT3 course, but due to the lack of time there was no possibility for comments on our work, which would have been very useful."

The group work during RMT3 course: "Exploring gaps and challenges in the transfer of research results" was positively commented on by several ESRs:

"Thank you for leaving time to work in groups and share reflections among us during the summer school. We always learn so much from these exchanges and we also very much appreciate saving some workload in preparation of the summer school."

"I enjoyed seeing the different communication methods and tools the different PhD students have been using. When preparing the assignment with my team, the discussion was very rich, and we learned from each other's processes and barriers..."

However, the same comment also highlighted time constraints:

"...But when presenting to the rest, as the time was limited, there was no possibility to discuss or suggest improvements to each of us."

Overall course evaluation

The online survey for RMT3 course was completed by 11 ESRs. The RMT3 course received good ratings and some positive comments on the course covering diverse and informative topics, providing valuable insights from experts (Table 5).

Table 5. RMT3 Summary of the overall evaluation

Questions	Answers	Average
Evaluate RMT3 course	11	3,7
How would you rate the overall organization of the on-line and in-person activities of the RMT3 course?	11	3,8

The fact that the course implemented various research methods was highlighted and was considered particularly beneficial for those focusing on methods like walking interviews and focus groups. The coordinators' responsiveness in inviting relevant researchers was greatly appreciated, enhancing the learning experience.

"Interesting topics! Thank you for organising it and for the good quality. "

"It was a very informative course. It is highly valuable that we were able to have access to lessons learnt coming from experts' experiences. "

"The lectures on the different research methods became very useful. In my case specially the ones about walking interviews and focus groups as they are more related to the methods I have used or will be using. "

"The challenge of communicating research output to non-academic audiences is pivotal for research projects that are dealing with complex societal issues like housing. The course offered us the chance to reflect on this and try to convey the aspects of our research to other stakeholders. "

"Coordinators considered what we asked for and invited researchers to give us examples and that was helpful. "

The two negative feedback mainly concerned the structure, clarity and the need for more personalised learning opportunities.

"The overall structure and clarity of the course were acceptable but could be significantly improved. Some of the sessions were not properly prepared, especially the invited participants who presented their work."

"I would have appreciated more tailor-made learning opportunities."

The organization of the on-line and in-person activities of the RMT3 course also got a good rating. The ESRs highlighted the thoughtfully structured courses with carefully chosen guest speakers addressing diverse module facets.

"Very well organized especially the guests' lectures. "

"The activities and guest speakers were carefully chosen to cover the different aspects of the module."

"In general it was well organised, and the on-line lectures were announced with enough time in advance so that the ESRs could plan their schedule around them."

"Coordinators would send us an email with the link to join the meeting. In-person activities were also a good opportunity to learn more about each other research."

One negative comment being provided as well:

„Acceptable, but could be improved by better matching the learning requirements with what was actually provided.“

For each online session, evaluations were conducted on a scale from 1 to 5, culminating in an overall positive rating (average 3.98) (Table 6).

Table 6. RMT3 Summary of the online session evaluation.

Questions	Answers	Average
Session 3 (April 19, 2023)	11	4,0
Session 4 (April 25, 2023)	11	3,9
Session 5 (May 16, 2023)	11	3,6
Session 6 (May 23, 2023)	11	4,4
Session 7 (May 23, 2023)	9	4,0

Almost all feedback received regarding the courses was positive. Below are the comments on the individual sessions.

Session 3

“Nice overview of methodologies and tools.“

“I found this lecture especially interesting as I learned how through the walking interviews one could explore the issues of people in relationship with the space. Until that moment I would not think of this as a research method, but I know see the high relevance it has for certain studies related to spatial or urban situations. “

“The session allowed us to explore and consider complementary methodologies. “

“It is not relevant to my current research; however, the idea of mental mapping was a really interesting idea to use for future research. “

Session 4

“As when attending this lecture I had not done yet my semi-structured interviews I could learn here some of the recommendations and mistakes to avoid which seemed interesting as for example paying attention to the non-verbal gestures, making interpretative questions if something is not clear or making indirect questions. “

“Very insightful session with practical examples and suggestions. “

“It was very useful, and I wish we had it in the first year. Thank you for it! “

Session 5

“It was very interesting and useful for the researchers who are working with vulnerable groups. Probably not as relevant for everyone. “

“Questions at the end were useful and answered some confusion we had. But I wish the presentation had more focus techniques of the interviews itself and advice on dealing with vulnerable groups. “

“Very insightful session with practical examples and suggestions. “

Session 6

“This lecture was very relevant for me as, even though I haven't done any focus group yet, I am planning to do some next year. I found especially interesting the opportunity that focus groups have create synergies between different stakeholders, obtaining maybe less in-depth data but giving more importance to the group dynamics. I learned about the importance of creating a clear structure and agenda, of going from general to specific questions and about the importance of having a varied composition of the group for better results. I will definitely continue researching about this method as the high quality of a moderator will determine the quality of the research outcome. “

“Very relevant as it is a common research method that can be applied to a vast range of studies. “

“Amazing and useful. Professor Joris is experienced and replied to our questions. “

Session 7

“Very insightful session with practical examples and suggestions. “

“It was very interesting for researchers who are not social scientists. “

“New methods and very useful and open our minds to new possibilities of using mobile to collect data. “

Only one non-positive feedback was received on Session 5.

“I found this lecture less practical in terms of how to apply the knowledge into my own research methods. “

The ESRs were asked to elaborate on the sessions that most met their expectations and explain the reasons for their choice. The ESRs found particular value in sessions focusing on stakeholder interviews, focus groups, and innovative research methods. These sessions, especially Sessions 3 and 6, resonated well as they aligned closely with the methodologies pertinent to their research projects, offering practical and relatable insights. Overall, the well-structured course comprehensively covered diverse research interests, providing relevant and applicable information beneficial to each participant's individual research endeavours.

“Stakeholder interviews and results - barriers and techniques.“

“Focus groups, helped me in preparing a study.“

“The sessions that were of best use for me were the sessions of the interviews, the innovative methods and tools.“

“All sessions were complementary to each other and provided a great overview of useful tool and experiences.“

“Session 3 and session 6 best met my expectations probably because I could relate the information with the research methods I have or will be implementing for my study, which made the lectures truly useful. “

“Overall, the course was well organised and tried to cover most of our research interests. So, everyone could find relevant information that could be applied to their research project. “

“Session 6. it was straight to the point and giving practical advice. “

For each learning outcomes of RMT3, evaluations were conducted on a scale from 1 to 5, culminating in an overall medium rating (average 3.45) (Table 7).

Table 7. RMT3 Summary of the learning outcomes evaluation

Questions	Answers	Average
Ability to engage with external stakeholders (non-academic sectors, local administrations, civic organizations), dealing with sustainable and affordable housing	11	3,6
An understanding the differences between the various communication methods to target specific non-academic groups	10	3,7
Ability to select the most suitable methods to communicate housing research findings from different disciplines to specific groups	10	3,5
Ability to position their own research results and those of other ESRs within the context of targeted stakeholders, ensuring that their findings are appropriately communicated and understood	11	3,4
Ability to prepare a transdisciplinary dissemination proposal, considering the needs and perspectives of all relevant stakeholders	11	3,0
A comprehensive understanding of the transdisciplinary approach to sustainable and affordable housing	11	3,5

The comments received are presented below in connection with the specific learning outcome.

Learning outcome 1

“Some of these lectures have helped me improve my interviewing skills when engaging with stakeholders from industry. “

“The objective of the course was achieved as it enabled us to reflect on previous experiences dealing with these actors. The activities were useful for crafting the key message of our research.“

“I learned from the stories they shared with us. “

Learning outcome 2

“That was a very important contribution of the course. “

“As mentioned above, the activities allowed us to reflect on the best communication channels and ways to approach different audiences“.

“Each community might have something different to motivate them to speak to researcher and collaborate. “

Learning outcome 3

“Theoretically yes but I didn't have the chance to apply this yet. “

“As mentioned above, the activities allowed us to reflect on the best communication channels and ways to approach different audiences. “

“No this part was not clear. “

Learning outcome 4

“This is still not applied in my case. “

“As mentioned above, the activities allowed us to reflect on the best communication channels and ways to approach different audiences. “

“We understood more about each other topics. “

Learning outcome 5

“This is a very big challenge that would probably require teamwork. “

“As mentioned above, the activities allowed us to reflect on the best communication channels and ways to approach different audiences. “

“No, this part was not clear. “

Learning outcome 6

“As mentioned above, the activities allowed us to reflect on the best communication channels and ways to approach different audiences. “

“Somehow yes, through the examples that presenters shared with us. “

The ESRs were asked to explain how the RMT3 course has contributed to the development of their research. According to the ESRs, the course significantly improved interviewing skills and data collection methods as it provided insights into different research methods and practical advice from experts. It influenced interviewing techniques and improved communication strategies for sharing research findings in future project phases.

“Yes, to some extent, particularly in the interview sessions.“

“It has helped me better understand the tools and methods that we have, and make better use of them. “

“It was invaluable to listen to experts sharing their knowledge and experiences. Their tips remain in my mind and are used at many levels throughout conducting my research. “

“It has helped to have an overall picture of different research methods applied in projects, as well as understanding some of the tips and mistakes to avoid when using these methods. “

“It gave me very good insights into interviewing and collecting data with different kinds of participants. The activities about communicating research findings were a good exercise for future stages of the project. “

“Change in the way I ask interview questions. “

ESRs had the opportunity to provide additional feedback regarding their experiences in the RMT3 course. The course was commended for its efforts to improve sessions and a comprehensive set of content. Suggestions included more personal interaction with specific instructors regarding individual research methods and streamlining assignments to focus on key lecture experiences. It was also appreciated that the coordinators responded to suggestions made prior to the course and improved subsequent sessions.

“Thanks to the course coordinators, who tried to level up the session. However, it could be better organised by involving the ESR in the work and sessions. “

“Assignments felt a bit unnecessary. The lectures themselves were the most important experience.“

“It would have been great to organise one-to-one sessions with the most related lecturer to each of our methods, so that we could present our research plan, how are we implementing these methods, and get personalised feedback from them, as specialists on the matter. “

“Thank you for the effort in assembling such a diverse and comprehensive module.“

“I am grateful for the course coordinator listening to us and adjusting the sessions' content to respond to what we suggested in a pre-course online meeting. This one was better and more useful.“

Annex 1 – Evaluation survey

RE-DWELL RMT 3 course – Quality assessment

1. How would you rate the overall organization of the online and face-to-face activities of the RMT3 course? (from 1 to 5)

2. How would you evaluate the following online sessions (from 1 to 5):

- a) SESSION 3 (19.04.23): Exploring innovative methodologies and tools
- b) SESSION 4 (25.04.23): Stakeholder interviews and results - barriers and techniques
- c) SESSION 5 (16.05.23): Interviews with vulnerable groups
- d) SESSION 6 (23.05.23): Focus groups
- e) SESSION 7 (23.05.23): Smart social sciences

3. Please explain which sessions best met your expectations and why.

- a) Open answer

4. Please explain in which ways has the RMT3 course contributed to the development of your research?

- b) Open answer

5. Please indicate to what extent the RMT3 learning outcomes have been achieved (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)

- a) Ability to engage with external stakeholders (non-academic sectors, local administrations, civic organizations), dealing with sustainable and affordable housing.
- b) An understanding the differences between the various communication methods to target specific non-academic groups.
- c) Ability to select the most suitable methods to communicate housing research findings from different disciplines to specific groups.
- d) Ability to position their own research results and those of other ESRs within the context of targeted stakeholders, ensuring that their findings are appropriately communicated and understood.
- e) Ability to prepare a transdisciplinary dissemination proposal, considering the needs and perspectives of all relevant stakeholders.
- f) A comprehensive understanding of the transdisciplinary approach to sustainable and affordable housing, including the importance of interdisciplinary collaboration, communication and engagement of the stakeholders involved.

6. Additional feedback regarding to your experience in this course?

- c) Open answer